

**Report on
GATE Workshop at Metascience Conference 2025:
Implementing Open Science for Communities**

Milestone

Report on GATE Workshop
Unconference | Metascience Conference London, 01 July, 2025

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Table of contents

1. Introduction to and strategy of the GATE Workshop at the Metascience Conference 2025
 - 1.1. Workshop part 1: About the GATE Initiative
 - 1.2. Workshop part 2: Strategy and structure
2. Targeted actions to advance Open Science developed in the workshop
3. Next steps

1. Introduction to the GATE Workshop at the Metascience Conference 2025

On **July 1st, 2025**, the GATE Initiative held a workshop at the [Metascience Conference 2025: Implementing Open Science for Communities - the GATE Workshop](#). The Metascience Conference took place in London from June 30 to July 2, 2025, and included stakeholders from research, publication, and funding. The GATE Workshop aimed to collaboratively identify the needs of specific Open Science target groups and develop targeted actions to advance Open Science. Specifically, participants were to be empowered to (1) construct supportive measures for their Open Science communities based on GATE Data and to (2) apply these concrete impulses within their institutions.

Figure 1: Promotion of GATE's workshop at the Metascience conference

1.1. Workshop part 1: About the GATE Initiative

The aim of the GATE Initiative is **1) to establish a continuous knowledge exchange on Open Science** guiding thoughts, practices, and their developments among various Open Science stakeholder groups and thus to provide guidance to various communities about the state of Open Science and its development, and **2) to promote high-quality informative and educational capacities connected to trustworthy repositories or catalogues**. Therefore, it serves as an effective infrastructure that promotes updated Open Science capacities and a highly relevant knowledge source for identifying the current and future state of Open Science. GATE thus enables Stakeholders who aim to foster Open Science within their communities (such as educators and knowledge creators, representatives of communities, policymakers, data infrastructure providers, funders, and researchers) to align their materials with the newest developments or to derive new (research) questions, targeted actions or policies for their communities.

The workshop was conducted by Marie Alavi, Rebecca Fischer, and Tom van Drimmelen, who acted as moderators for the group work, supported by GATE's research lead, Julia Priess-Buchheit. At the beginning of the workshop, Marie Alavi provided an overview of the current collaborators of the GATE Initiative, as well as its goals and the process of data collection.

1.2. Workshop part 2: Strategy and structure

Before the GATE Workshop, a pre-conference phase invited [Open Science Knowledge Creators](#) (speakers, authors, trainers, and developers of materials that foster and reflect Open Science, including reports, leaflets, training sessions, and articles) to connect their resources to GATE. They provided information about the guiding thoughts in their materials through a questionnaire called the [GATE Service](#) (which is continuously open to engage with). This information, known as *GATE Data*, formed the basis of the workshop's content and included data and resources from organisations/projects such as NFDI, CLARIN, ZBW, the OPTIMA Project, and EOSC.

The workshop was held on-site as an informal and participative unconference session, with 18 participants from research and funding. Its **goal was to develop targeted, supportive capacity-building measures to advance Open Science in specific communities**. In an introductory round, participants identified the target groups/Open Science communities (referred to as *Personas*) they represented and grouped with peers from the same research ecosystem.

Figure 2: GATE's lifecycle, targeted Communities, Supporters and Collaborators

They then **collaboratively identified challenges and needs for their personas based on GATE Data and developed supportive and targeted actions together.**

To facilitate the workshop, the moderators provided materials, including *Persona* descriptions and a selection of previously submitted *data* (general Open Science guiding thoughts and those at the intersection with AI). Participants formed three groups representing the following personas and selected the following guiding thoughts as a basis for co-creative actions:

Persona	Selected guiding thoughts
Early Career Researcher (research role)	Transparency, Explainability
Senior Researcher (research role)	Responsibility, “as open as possible-as - as closed as necessary”, data confidentiality
Open Access Officer (support role)	Integrity, Responsibility, Traceability

Table 1: Personas chosen in the workshop (representing Open Science communities) and the underlying Open Science guiding thoughts for developing targeted actions.

2. Targeted actions to advance Open Science were developed in the workshop

Group 1: Persona – Early Career Researcher

A larger group primarily comprised (junior and senior) Researchers, who developed an action based on the guiding thoughts *Transparency* and *Explainability* (being important for science communication) for the community of Early Career Researchers (ERC; see Figure 3).

Action: Using Open-lab Workbooks provides a better overview and documentation of ERC's progress and best practice examples. This enhances ERCs' motivation, credibility, and reuse possibilities of one's own work and supports *transparency* (often undermined by systemic issues such as funding and publication pressure) and *explainability* for a more reliable science communication.

Figure 3: Persona group 1

Group 2: Persona – Senior researcher

Group 2 included participants from education and research, representing the Senior Researcher community in the workshop (see Figure 4). Based on the selected guiding thoughts, *Responsibility, as open as possible - as closed as necessary, and data confidentiality*, they developed the following **Actions** for this persona group, addressing their challenges and needs:

- Organising internal “code checks” at departments and institutions before publishing (as it is already practised and partly institutionalised in the Netherlands). Such code checks reduce the likelihood of mistakes left in one’s own codes and thus increase the willingness to share the code. Nevertheless, this involves costs for the institutions.
- Work in trusted repositories to maintain data confidentiality - also cost-affiliated.
- Leverage existing “federated data systems” that analyse the data submitted, while the data stays in the system and ensures data confidentiality.

RESEARCH ROLE
Persona Dr. Tomasz, 56, Senior Researcher in Medicine

Tomasz leads several clinical research projects and has decades of experience publishing in top-tier medical journals. He is cautious about Open Science, particularly about patient confidentiality and data misuse. He sees the benefits but prefers low-risk, low-effort solutions.

Challenges

- “Open Science? What’s the real added value?”
- “I’ve always published in closed top journals—why change?”
- “Worried that errors or critics will find my data.”
- “Patient confidentiality is non-negotiable.”

Needs

- “Show me evidence that openness boosts impact and reproducibility.”
- “Give me low-risk, easy tools that fit my workflow.”
- “Secure, compliant paths to share anonymized patient data.”

Figure 4: Persona group 2

Group 3: Persona – Open Access Officer

The third group included researchers as well as one publisher and concentrated on the guiding principles of *Integrity, Traceability, and Responsibility*. The group developed three supporting **Actions** for Open Access Officers (see Figure 5):

- Establish persistent identifiers (PID) and requirements at various sectors of the research ecosystem to allow optimum traceability, including leveraging AI to capture additional information.
- Use established systems by submitting data into existing databases and connecting to other repositories (instead of waiting for ideal systems to be ready).
- Use and support the development of tools (including AI) supporting reproducibility checks (including the validity of data and the analysis).
- Establish processes for funders and fundees to support Open Science.

SUPPORT ROLE (Data/Open Access)
Persona Sandra, 38, Open Access Officer

Sandra coordinates the university’s open access strategy. She manages the institutional repository, advises researchers on publishing options, and monitors compliance with funder mandates.

Challenges

- “People see me as ‘paperwork police,’ not a partner.”
- “OA mandates vary by funder/publisher—so confusing.”
- “Budget for APCs is tiny; transformative deals are complex.”
- “I must constantly justify my role and OA’s value.”

Needs

- “Slide decks and infographics to explain OA benefits.”
- “Faculty and admin buy-in for OA strategy.”
- “Automated compliance, APC tracking tools.”
- “Recognition as a strategic research enabler.”

Figure 5: Persona group 3

3. Outcomes and Next Steps

The overall data collected by GATE as of today reveals manifold information on the state of Open Science for various communities. One way to leverage GATE Data is to identify concrete expectations, needs and challenges to Open Science as shown in the following example (Figure 6):

Leveraging GATE data: Thematic Summary of present general guiding thoughts

Education & Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training in open science from early career stages • Integration of open practices into curricula • Support for student-led and collaborative projects
Collaboration & Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary and international cooperation • Bottom-up initiatives and best practice sharing • Shift toward a culture of openness and responsibility
Accessibility & Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and open access to research outputs • No paywalls or technical barriers • Inclusive participation across regions and disciplines
Openness & Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open methods, data, and results • Reproducibility and accountability • Scientific integrity and trust
Policy & Public Good	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible research assessment (beyond impact factors) • Alignment with global policies (e.g. EU, UNESCO) • Knowledge as a public good, not a commodity

Figure 6: Summary of main guiding thoughts collected by GATE in 2025

This summary of GATE data shows that transparent, collaborative, and accessible science is a valuable means to foster trust, equity, and innovation, but real change requires both individual action and systemic reform. The workshop showcased GATE’s features for collective efforts to advance Open Science, enabling representatives from different communities to identify needs and challenges and co-create supporting actions that foster Open Science for their target groups. The GATE Initiative will proceed with the following steps:

1. **Continuous community building and data collection:** Further engage Open Science Communities (Knowledge Creators, Community Representatives, Data Infrastructure Providers, Policymakers, Funder and Researchers) into the GATE process to submit knowledge on Open Science to the [GATE Service](#).
2. **Refine data modelling and structure the GATE data** for specific stakeholders.
3. **Publish GATE Report 2025** in early 2026 (provide **guidance to optimisation** of Open Science capacities, **highlight intersected capacities and infrastructures**).
4. **Foster iterative collaboration**, including needs assessment with community stakeholders and co-creating workshops.

The GATE initiative, as a cooperative, transparent, and non-profit effort, continues to establish itself as a trustworthy solution to build and maintain Open Science capacities. For more information or to join the GATE service, visit www.openscienceGATE.com.